

Some Structural Aspects of Pyrrolidinate Mixed Ligand Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and their Antifungal Activity

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Structural studies of the mixed ligand complexes of the type $[M(\text{pyr})_2\text{L}]2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[M'(\text{pyr})_2\text{L}]$ ($M = \text{Co}^{2+}$ or Ni^{2+} ; $M' = \text{Cu}^{2+}$; Hpyr = pyrrolidine; L = 1,2-diamino ethane or 1,2-diamino propane) are reported. The complexes have been isolated in solid state and characterised by elemental analysis, spectral (visible and ir) data and room temperature magnetic measurements. Six coordinate cobalt and nickel complexes show distorted octahedral geometry whereas four coordinate copper complexes are square planer. Proton affinity behaviour studied in complex-HCl (dry) equilibria shows structural alterations other than simple ligand/anion protonation. Antifungal activity of these complexes against *Botryodiplodia theobromae* (incitant of fruit rot of apple) is also reported.

ISOLATION and structure determination of mixed ligand complexes having pyrrolidinate anion and 1,2-ethanediamine and 1,2-propanediamine as ligands are described here. The probable structures of the complexes have been assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility data, diffuse reflectance spectra and ir measurements. Proton affinity behaviour has been studied in solid-gas equilibria existing between complex-HCl (g, dry) system using sorption, desorption and ir spectra of HCl-addition products. The toxicity of some of these complexes against a pathogenic fungal isolate of *Botryodiplodia theobromae* (apple strain) is also reported.

Experimental

The starting materials $M(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$M = \text{Co(II)}$, Ni(II) and $\text{Hpyr} = \text{pyrrolidine}$] and $M(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$M = \text{Cu(II)}$] have been isolated by refluxing calculated quantities of sodium pyrrolidinate^{1,2} and solutions of $M(\text{II})$ nitrate hexahydrate in 200 ml acetone for about 10-12 hr. The pyrrolidinate salts of cobalt, nickel and copper are yellowish brown, light green and greenish blue, respectively. The compounds were dried over P_2O_5 and used as starting materials for isolation of mixed ligand complexes. Amine complexes have been isolated by shaking $M(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$M = \text{Co(II)}$, Ni(II)] and $\text{Cu}(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with 'en' and 'pn' in about 50 ml acetone for about 10 days. Formation of the complexes is marked by change in colour and particle size. The complexes were filtered, washed with acetone and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl_2 before analysis.

The procedure suggested by Schilt and Kenneth was adopted^{3,4} for the study of proton affinity behaviour. The complex-HCl (g, dry) equilibria was tried to study the proton affinity behaviour. The complexes were weighed before and after exposure to anhydrous HCl to know if the solid-gas system would provide evidence for proton affinity of the complexes. The nature of the sorbed HCl was studied both by measuring the weight loss by vapourisation under prolonged evacuation and by estimation of chloride ions after extraction of the acid adducts with water. IR spectra of acid adducts were also used to investigate the nature of the sorbed HCl gas.

Analysis: The complexes were analysed for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen by the Coleman analyser. Co(II) and Cu(II) were estimated by pyridine method⁵ and nickel(II) as nickel dimethylglyoximate⁶. Magnetic susceptibility have been measured at room temperature using Gouy balance. Infrared spectra were recorded by Perkin Elmer No. 5100 4366 IR spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade.

Toxicity study: Preliminary tests were made against three phytopathogenic fungi, *Alternaria solani*, *Rhizopus nodosus* and *Botryodiplodia theobromae*, and the organism most susceptible to the mixed ligand complexes was selected for further study. Toxicity was determined by measuring mycelial growth after 5 days of incubation of the fungus at 28° in Czapek Dox liquid media amended with different concentrations of chemicals. All chemicals were used as fine aqueous suspensions. Dry mycelial weight of the resulting cultures was

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TABLE 1—ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC MEASUREMENTS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
				C	H	N	M	
1.	Co(pyr) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Co(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Brown	34.78 (35.42)	8.03 (8.94)	9.49 (10.39)	22.51 (21.72)	4.98
2.	Co(pyr) ₂ (en).2H ₂ O	Co(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ (C ₂ H ₈ N ₂).2H ₂ O	Dark brown	40.63 (40.67)	8.68 (9.58)	19.91 (19.10)	20.08 (19.95)	5.01
3.	Co(pyr) ₂ (pn).2H ₂ O	Co(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ (C ₂ H ₁₀ N ₂).2H ₂ O	Dark brown	42.23 (42.71)	9.03 (9.79)	17.98 (18.28)	19.73 (19.04)	5.03
4.	Ni(pyr) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Ni(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Light green	35.01 (35.43)	9.51 (8.90)	10.97 (10.40)	21.98 (21.66)	8.26
5.	Ni(pyr) ₂ (en).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Ni(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ (C ₂ H ₈ N ₂).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Light grey	35.91 (36.27)	10.13 (9.74)	17.41 (17.08)	17.29 (17.13)	3.37
6.	Ni(pyr) ₂ (pn).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Ni(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ (C ₂ H ₁₀ N ₂).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Light grey	37.81 (38.27)	9.43 (9.93)	16.93 (16.34)	17.57 (17.01)	3.31
7.	Cu(pyr) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Cu(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Greenish blue	39.71 (40.06)	8.73 (8.40)	11.49 (11.75)	26.03 (26.49)	1.87
8.	Cu(pyr) ₂ (en)	Cu(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ (C ₂ H ₈ N ₂)	Brown	45.10 (45.50)	9.61 (9.17)	21.01 (21.37)	24.65 (24.07)	1.86
9.	Cu(pyr) ₂ (pn)	Cu(C ₄ H ₉ N) ₂ (C ₂ H ₁₀ N ₂)	Brown	47.21 (47.50)	9.07 (9.44)	21.12 (20.99)	23.23 (22.86)	1.78

pyr = pyrrolidine, en = 1,2-ethanediamine, pn = 1,2-propanediamine.

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL BAND POSITIONS IN REFLECTANCE SPECTRA WITH PROBABLE ASSIGNMENT AND CALCULATION OF LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS (VALUES IN cm⁻¹)

Compound	Observed band and their assignments		Calculated parameters		
	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{1g} (F)	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	B	β*	Dq
Co(pyr) ₂ .4H ₂ O	15680	22730	874	0.78	899
Co(pyr) ₂ (en).2H ₂ O	16670	21740	834	0.74	801
Co(pyr) ₂ (pn).2H ₂ O	16390	22220	915	0.81	878
$\beta = \frac{B}{B_0} = \frac{B}{1120}$ (where B ₀ = the Racah parameter value in the free ion state)					
	⁴ A _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (F)	⁴ A _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	B	β*	Dq
Ni(pyr) ₂ .4H ₂ O	14710	26320	967	0.89	884
Ni(pyr) ₂ (en).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	16670	27030	825	0.77	1064
Ni(pyr) ₂ (pn).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	15150	26670	959	0.89	914
$\beta = \frac{B}{B_0} = \frac{B}{1080}$ (where B ₀ = the Racah parameter value in the free ion state)					

*B. N. Figgis, "Introduction to Ligand Field", Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1976, p. 52.

determined and per cent inhibition of growth (dosage-growth response) was graphically plotted on logarithmic-probit scale. ED₅₀ values were obtained by interpolation from straight lines on logarithmic probability paper.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis and magnetic measurements (Table 1) show that pyrrolidine complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) with 'en' or 'pn' as ligand are six coordinate while those of Cu(II) are four coordinate. Ni(II) complexes possess two lattice water molecules outside the coordination sphere. Magnetic moments of Co(II) complexes in 'oh' field having ground state ⁴T₁ usually lie in the range 4.7-5.2 B.M.⁷. The μ_{eff} value for Co(II) has been found in the 4.98-5.03 B.M. range. For bivalent nickel complexes, it is found in the 3.26-3.31 B.M. range which is within the reported range (2.9-3.4 B.M.) for 'oh' complexes having

two unpaired electrons^{8,9}. Cu(II) complexes have magnetic moment in the range 1.78-1.87 B.M. which is the reported range for square planer complexes (1.79-2.03 B.M.) having 'D_{4h}' symmetry^{10,11}.

Spectral studies : Brown coloured six coordinate complexes of Co(II) show 2-3 bands in the visible region of the reflectance spectra. Table 2 records B, β and Dq values calculated on the basis of energy level diagrams¹²⁻¹⁵. The third and the highest energy band is observed around 21740-22730 cm⁻¹ which may be due to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) transition. A second band in the range 15630-16670 cm⁻¹ is observed which corresponds to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{1g}(F) transition. The visible bands are found to possess one shoulder which may be attributed to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{1g} transition but its origin appears to be in spin orbit coupling or vibrational broadening. The interelectronic repulsion parameter 'B' is reduced to about 74-81% of the free ion value

TABLE 3—INTERACTION OF SOLID COMPLEXES WITH DRY HYDROGEN CHLORIDE GAS

Compound	Sorption of HCl		Desorption of HCl			
	Colour change	Moles HCl/ Moles Cpd	Prolonged	Evacuation	Washing with water	
			Colour change	Moles HCl/ Moles Cpd*	Change	% HCl removed
Co(pyr) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Brown→ light violet	3.91	None	2.86	dissolves	—
Co(pyr) ₂ (en).2H ₂ O	Dark brown→ dark green	3.96	None	2.83	do	—
Co(pyr) ₂ (pn).2H ₂ O	Dark brown→ dark green	3.73	None	2.80	do	—
Ni(pyr) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Light green→ yellow	3.17	None	2.93	do	—
Ni(pyr) ₂ (en).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Light grey→ pale orange	6.13	None	5.20	do	—
Ni(pyr) ₂ (pn).2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Light grey→ pale orange	6.15	None	5.23	do	—
Cu(pyr) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Greenish blue→ light green	3.18	None	2.69	do	—
Cu(pyr) ₂ (en)	Brown→yellow	3.39	None	2.91	do	—
Cu(pyr) ₂ (pn)	Brown→yellow	3.41	None	2.83	do	—

*Moles of HCl remaining per mole of complex after two or more days in a vacuum dessicator subjected to periodic evacuation.

 TABLE 4—PRINCIPAL INFRARED FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) of MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

Co(pyr) ₂ . 4H ₂ O	Co(pyr) ₂ (en). 2H ₂ O	Co(pyr) ₂ (pn). 2H ₂ O	Ni(pyr) ₂ . 4H ₂ O	Ni(pyr) ₂ (en). 2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Ni(pyr) ₂ (pn). 2H ₂ O.2H ₂ O	Cu(pyr) ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Cu(pyr) ₂ . (en)	Cu(pyr) ₂ . (pn)
515	440 520*	435 520*	470	490 520*	460 535	430 510	460 525*	515*
	580 780	570 780	650 840*	650 685*	655 840*	675 780	835*	700
840*	840*	840*	870*	980 1025	875*	875*	885	840*
	875	875			930 1020*		975	1020*
1005	1060*	1015 1040	1000* 1070		1045	1055*	1020 1050*	1060*
	1120 1160	1110 1130		1155* 1275*	1200		1100* 1165*	
1320*			1315*		1305	1345		
1390	1390*	1390	1385	1385*	1460	1385	1385*	1385*
1485	1460 1550	1460 1570	1490	1455*		1420*	1445* 1580*	1450 1590*
1620	1620	1630	1620	1600	1585	1620		
2425*	2425*	2415*	2440*	2440* 2880*	2440* 2870*	2425* 2870*	2425*	2425*
			2920	2950	2925* 2960*	2930	2960	2980
				8160 8240	8150		8130	8125
	3200*	3190		3280*	3260		3220	3220
3480	3460	3420	3440 3640	3470 3630	3420 3640*	3430 3540	3380	3400

*Denotes the more intense bands.

(1120 cm⁻¹). Calculated values of ν_1 are in the range 7400-8100 cm⁻¹.

Diffuse reflectance spectra of the Ni(II) complexes are characterised by three spin allowed transitions. The band at ν_1 , equal to 10 Dq, is assigned to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ transition, the second band in the 14710-16670 cm⁻¹ region is due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transition whereas the third band in the region 26320-27030 cm⁻¹ corresponds to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition. The ligand field parameters 'B', 'β' and 'Dq' have been calculated with the help of the energy level diagram for d⁸ ions in cubic field^{4,16}. The ν_2 band shows a shoulder which may be due

to the gain of intensity of ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ transition through interaction with ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ level^{17,18}. The Racah parameter 'B' of the complexes has been found about 77-89% of the free ion value (1080 cm⁻¹).

In reflectance spectra of Cu(II) complexes only one characteristic absorption maxima is observed in the 13700-18500 cm⁻¹ range along with a weak absorption in some cases. In case of strong distortion this band is observed around 18000 cm⁻¹ or even higher¹⁶. For 'pn' complex (No. 9) the band is observed around 18520 cm⁻¹ which indicates distortion from planer geometry²⁰. The value of λ_{max} has been taken to be equal to 10 Dq.

Infrared spectra : IR spectra of the complexes (Table 4) were examined for M-N stretching, N-N stretching, N-H banding and skeletal ring vibration. We have observed M-N absorption in the form of one to two bands in the range 610-500 cm^{-1} except in the case of $\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where it is observed at 470 cm^{-1} which can also be assigned as infrared active Ni-N stretching mode^{21,22}. The positions of M-N stretching vibrations in these complexes are in agreement with the usual M-N bands²³. Bivalent cobalt and nickel complexes (Nos. 1-6) have water molecules in their coordination sphere. This coordinated water molecule is expected to show the rocking and the infrared active M-O stretching if M-O bond is sufficiently covalent in nature. Fujita²⁴ and Gamo²⁵ observed these bands at 880-650 cm^{-1} . We also find two bands, one around 840 cm^{-1} and the other around 680-650 cm^{-1} . Other (M-O) stretching vibrations are observed at 440, 435, 470, 490, 460 and 430 cm^{-1} , respectively²⁶.

Infrared studies of Ni(II) complexes show presence of lattice water molecules²⁷, which absorb at 3440-3605 cm^{-1} along with HOH weak bending absorption around 1600 cm^{-1} . Other principal bands of amine complexes examined are N-H stretching asymmetric (3350 cm^{-1}), N-H bending (1650-1550 cm^{-1}), C-N vibration (1030 \pm 30 cm^{-1}) and skeletal ring vibration. C=C ring vibrations are observed in the form of 2-3 bands in the range 1590-1450 cm^{-1} . On coordination, a shift in the N-H bending vibration of amine is noted which indicates electron delocalisation and hence coordination through N atoms. The spectra of amine complexes can be discussed in the light of the reported data^{28,29} by noting N-H stretching bands.

Proton affinity studies : Table 3 summarises the proton affinity behaviour observed in complex-HCl

(g, dry) equilibrium. It was observed that on sorption the ratio (moles HCl)/(moles Cpd) was 3.73-3.96 for six coordinate Co(II) complexes. This ratio for bivalent nickel complexes lies at \sim 6.15 whereas the same for Cu(II) 'D_{4h}' complexes lies in the range 3.13-3.41. About one mole of HCl, which appears to be loosely bound, is given out on prolonged evacuation. When treated with water, the solid HCl-adducts instead of reverting back to the respective mixed ligand complexes, either decompose or dissolve with almost complete removal of HCl. The ir spectra of HCl-adducts suggest that protonation takes place at the ligand molecules. A shift in the N-H stretching (\sim 2950 cm^{-1}) and bending vibration of amines also indicates ligand protonation. Chatt and coworkers suggested that complexes of primary amine have a strong tendency to associate through intermolecular hydrogen bonds of NH-Cl type³⁰. A detailed study of ir spectra of HCl-adducts (Table 5) show that appreciable structural alternation takes place on addition of HCl (g). In general, the number of ir bands are reduced but appearance of some new bands indicates that structural changes other than simple protonation are also possible. The M-N, M-O and other absorption bands in the region 900-700 cm^{-1} display similar bands like those of untreated complexes. However, the question of protonation mechanism in complexes requires screening of many more complexes of different transition metals having pyrrolidine anion.

Toxicity studies : Data indicate that the three metal complexes differed in their fungitoxic action. Among cobalt complexes cobalt-pyrrolidinate tetrahydrate was more toxic than the 'pn' complex (Fig. 1). The extent of antifungal activity induced by the former was about 6 times higher than that

TABLE 5—PRINCIPAL INFRARED FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF HYDROGEN CHLORIDE ADDITION PRODUCTS OF SOLID COMPLEXES

$\text{Co}(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Co}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{en}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Co}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{pn}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{en}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{pn}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Cu}(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Cu}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{en}) \cdot x\text{HCl}$	$\text{Cu}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{pn}) \cdot x\text{HCl}$
665*					425*	460	460	500
700*		690*	595	595	635	690		
735*								
840	780	765*	750		750	750*	775*	710*
	880	865		800	800*			810*
	870		870*	865*	870*			
	890	905		1000*	975*			
	1000							
1045*	1055*		1040	1025*	1030*	1020*	1000*	1010*
			1070	1075	1065*	1065*	1050*	1080
1670	1105*	1105*						1150
1160*	1145	1130		1160	1155*			
1230	1200	1190		1310*	1210*	1220*	1330*	
1380	1360*		1380*	1345*	1305	1385*	1380*	1365*
					1345*			
1440*	1390	1400*			1385*	1400		
					1400			
	1460	1445*			1455	1445*	1455	
1485*	1480	1480*		1490	1485*	1485*	1480*	1490
					1565			
1530*	1580			1580	1585		1560*	1585
1605*	1610	1635	1610		1615	1610*		
3880								
3650	3420	3420	3400	3400	3410	3470	3075	3110
							3450	3430

*Denotes the more intense bands.

Fig. 1—Dosage-growth response curves against some mixed ligand metal complexes.

induced by the latter (Table 6). Nickel complexes with 'pn' or 'en' ligands were more or less equally toxic, as a parallelism in their dosage-response-curves is evident (Fig. 1). On the contrary, Cu mixed ligand complexes induced quite varied inhibitory effects. Cu^{2+} complex with 'pn' as secondary ligand was most effective against test pathogen

TABLE 6— ED_{50} VALUES OF SOLID METAL COMPLEXES AGAINST *B. theobromae*

Compound	IC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	ED_{50} ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
$\text{Co}(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	50	1100
$\text{Co}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{pn}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	50	7000
$\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{en}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$	200	2400
$\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{pn}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$	200	3000
$\text{Cu}(\text{pyr})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	100	>10,000
$\text{Cu}(\text{pyr})_2(\text{pn})$	100	640

ED_{50} : Concentration required to inhibit 50% mycelial growth.

IC : Initial concentration used.

($\text{ED}_{50} = 640 \mu\text{g/ml}$) while the copper $^{2+}$ pyrrolidinate dihydrate alone (without 'pn' as secondary ligand) could not suppress even 50 per cent of the fungal growth at a far higher concentration (i.e. >10,000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). In general, the inhibition of fungal growth increased gradually with the increase of concentration of complexes.

In a similar study, copper complexes exhibited greater antifungal activity than other metal complexes against *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *F. solani* and there also the complexes were more fungitoxic than the ligand alone 21 .

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